

Systematic Literature Review of Therapeutic Use of Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response
(ASMR) and Short-Term ASMR Auditory Training Trial

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Abstract

This thesis consists of 2-parts: a systematic review of current publications on therapeutic use of autonomous sensory meridian response (ASMR), and a within-subjects auditory training trial using ASMR videos. The main intent is to explore ASMR as potentially therapeutically beneficial for those with atypical sensory processing. Many hearing related disorders and mood or anxiety symptoms overlap with symptoms of sensory processing issues. For this reason, inclusion and exclusion criteria of the systematic review were generated in an effort to produce optimal search outcomes, and avoid overly confined criteria that would limit yielded results. Criteria for inclusion in the review for Part 1 are: (1) adult participants diagnosed with hearing loss or atypical sensory processing, (2) inclusion of measures related to ASMR as a treatment method and (3) published between 2000 and 2022. A total of 1,088 publications were found in preliminary search, and a total of 13 articles met inclusion criteria. A total of 14 participants completed the trial and post-trial questionnaire. Of all responses, 64.29% agreed that the duration of auditory training sessions was reasonable. In addition, 71.43% agreed that the training improved their perception of music. Lastly, 64.29% agreed that the training improved their perception of a primary talker when there are other talkers or background noises present.

Keywords: Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response, ASMR, Systematic Review, Auditory Training, Atypical Sensory Processing, Hearing Loss

Background of ASMR

What some may have sarcastically described as “licking microphones on camera for money” has emerged into something far more meaningful in the last 5 to 10 years. The phenomenon of Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response, or ASMR, has gained traction as a tool for self-soothing, rather than solely entertainment, amongst consumers in online platforms like Twitch or YouTube. While many creators earn income from their ASMR videos, many are content to create episodes as a hobby. A dedicated ASMR subgroup on Reddit contains 86,000 subscribers from around the world, and some of the most popular ASMR content creators on YouTube have about 300,000 subscribers (Poerio et al., 2018). ASMR has become the third most searched term on YouTube across the planet (Incadence, n.d.). This growth can be illustrated via a simple comparison to Zappavigna’s 2020 work, where at the time of writing they reported approximately 97,600,000 results from a basic Google video search for ASMR. By 2021 the same search yielded a greater result of about 274,000,000 (Buckley, 2022). Data showed that ASMR viewership more than doubled month-to-month in the year 2021 (Nelson, 2021; Michael, 2021).

A typical episode is something like this: the main character positions himself in close proximity to the camera, dressed like a bartender holding an empty drinking glass in one hand and towel in the other hand, wiping the inside of the glass clean as he gently yet cheerfully welcomes the viewer to the bar. The character carries on with a brief story about his day, and leans in to pour the viewer a drink and set the glass down in front of the viewer. This idea of speaking directly to the camera may not seem significantly different than when a news anchor speaks to the camera about the weather or world events, however it is the quality of the recorded sound and proximity to the camera that are key differentiators. High quality microphones are

used to record the character as he or she uses a calm whisper-like voice at a carefully modulated cadence, with smooth movements and softly manipulated props to emit sounds into the microphones at specific moments of the script. The combinations of these sounds, over a well-designed backdrop according to the theme of the video, are primarily what attract viewers who experience an infamous intra-cranial tingle sensation combined with chills and relaxation.

All content is not equal with regard to provoking a relaxing tingling sensation; not everyone who views or listens to ASMR content will experience the sensation, or is able to experience it. Viewers discover through trial and error specific types of sounds that trigger it. Aside from a whispered voice, other common triggers include the bristles of a hairbrush being gently ruffled, tapping beautifully manicured fingernails against various surfaces such as a keyboard, or running one's fingers through another's hair (Galante et al., 2019). For those unsure what an ASMR experience may be like, Dr. Richard (Hackett, 2021 and Richard, n.d.) makes a comparison to what many television viewers remember experiencing when watching the infamous 1980s show, "The Joy of Painting", hosted by Bob Ross. Bob Ross was known for his soothing vocal quality as he calmly demonstrated to the audience through each step of creating a painting.

There is a sense of social intimacy, albeit fabricated, which further cements people's attraction to ASMR and their ongoing subscription to ASMR channels. The characters' use of convincing expressions of care and affirmation provide viewers with a sense of genuineness. These types of videos became a sort-of social substitute during periods of heightened stress of the COVID-19 pandemic-driven social isolation (Buckley, 2022). Viewers do have a common boundary regarding this perceived benefit of social intimacy: evidence suggests that ASMR seeking is a non-sexual experience (Poerio et al., 2018).

In medical roleplays, the ASMRtist is the healthcare provider, and the viewer accepts the role as patient. Because this (and other role-play simulations in general) is inherently artificial, viewers temporarily suspend at least some of their real-world expectations of complete accuracy, which reinforces a successful ASMR trigger session. The ASMRtist finds “problems” by running tests on the viewer’s body (such as a nasal swab at certain angles toward the camera) and offers a treatment. Perhaps the ASMR roleplay doctor’s authority is comforting because the childhood ideal of the doctor who makes the sick patient better is preferable to the unknowns of modern medical treatment. Commenters regarded watching ASMR medical roleplay videos to alleviate their anxiety, depression, and pain. Like familiar media forms of television and film, diversion – an escape or emotional release – was another common gratification noted from a researcher’s analysis of 700 comments in 70 ASMR medical roleplay videos on YouTube (Frank, 2021). With the availability of medical information on the web, people may be vulnerable to developing a variation of hypochondria when anxious about a misinterpreted list of diseases and symptoms. In short, ASMR medical roleplay videos offer peace of mind under the guise of “healthcare”.

ASMR was initially perceived to be a pop-psychology fad within a niche genre of online multi-media by scholars who were dismissive of its merits due to lack of controlled peer reviewed studies. Early assumptions had been made about ASMR’s relation to synesthesia or frisson, and that any perceived benefit was some form of placebo or self-fulfilling prophecy. Yet, one early report found that, the chills of frisson often triggered by emotional music, tend to last about 10 seconds, whereas the tingling of ASMR tend to last several minutes or more (Fredborg et al., 2018). In one study, ASMR was further defined: autonomous refers to the personal ability to facilitate or produce the sensation at will. Sensory is defined as the sense organs transmitting nerve impulses to the brain or senses themselves in response to an external trigger. Meridian

refers to the highest point or apex, symbolized a sense of euphoria—in Eastern tradition, the meridian is used to illustrate the pathways taken by the qi, or life energy, as it flows through the human body. The participants described feeling as if time was passing quickly and that ASMR videos helped them to engage in their studies. Participants shared the positive interpersonal impact on relationships due to feeling more sensitive to the love of others after watching ASMR videos with affirmation and kindness themes (Chan et al., 2022).

In Fredborg et al.'s (2018) study, 284 individuals with ASMR completed the Toronto Mindfulness Scale (TMS), Mindful Attention and Awareness Scale (MAAS), and a questionnaire examining ASMR experiences. They essentially explored a possible relationship between ASMR and state (a transient moment-to-moment conscious experience) versus trait (more enduring tendency to experience the world in such manner) mindfulness. ASMR experiencers had significantly higher scores on the MAAS, a global measure of mindfulness, as well as significantly higher scores on the curiosity subscale of the TMS.

Training in communication and behavioral therapy can help people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) improve their cognitive and behavioral limitations, as well as self-regulating successfully. ASMR is hypothesized by one author to induce relaxation and emotional self-regulation necessary for those with ASD to help them navigate the symptoms of a melt-down from sensory hyperreactivity (Galante et al., 2019). However, the author also points out that ASMR stimuli should be selected with caution, as ASD may be comorbid with misophonia. A specific set of sounds may actually exacerbate emotional reactions as opposed to mitigating them.

Although not yet supported with empirical evidence, the above author's theory is anecdotally supported by an interview with a music producer named Nicholas, who has ASD.

Nicholas reports that “When I’m sometimes feeling stressed or on edge or I feel like I have too much energy, [ASMR] calms me down and soothes me in a way that makes me feel like I have weight off of me...The tingles went down from my head to my spine and the feeling at the same time was both relaxing and euphoric, and I started to enjoy the feeling...[the ASMRtist’s] voice was so calm...She would tell you to look into her eyes and she would put her hands to her temples and tell you to do it. She would do it in the same motion and it would feel like you were feeling her fingers on your temples, soothing side by side. Somehow it would feel so real but it’s not (Sleep Club, 2019).”

Healthcare professionals should be aware of the risks and therapeutic benefits of this emerging field of study. As with other alternative therapies like acupuncture and massage, patients may be ahead of the evidence-based literature in their use of ASMR for self-help, and they may seek information from their healthcare providers about its use. ASMR may interfere with certain aspects of executive function, suggesting that people should not engage in ASMR before performing dangerous tasks (such as operating heavy machinery) that require focused attention. Among participants who scored moderate to severe on the Beck Depression Inventory, 69% reported using ASMR to ease symptoms of depression (Reddy et al., 2020).

Curt Ramsey (n.d.) is an example of a professional who has implemented ASMR as a therapeutic supplement to traditional mental health services for his patients. He creates ASMR videos in which he vocalizes or producing specific trigger sounds as a form of “guided relaxation or meditations...to...further relax the client.” He also has incorporated ASMR triggers into counseling sessions. For instance, during a session with a married couple that was arguing with raised voices, whispering helped them not only regain composure but also see one another as more trustworthy, and move forward in reconciling with one another.

Interestingly, marketing professionals have begun to explore ASMR content for advertising. One study investigated the effectiveness of embedding ASMR within a negative green ad in controlling viewers' fear (Suci et al., 2023). It also explored the effects of ASMR on buying intention between two different perceived-difficulty eco-friendly products. The findings reveal that, compared to non-ASMR exposures, interplaying negative appeal with ASMR could significantly decrease young adults' fear. Secondly, a marketing agency created an advertisement using ASMR for a barber shop called Sport Clips (Wolf, 2023). The theme was “MVP Haircut Experience” and incorporated whispered vocalizations alternating binaurally in a stereo effect. Data analysis indicated that 100% of the tested audio scored at or above benchmarks for overall resonance, intent, and engagement. This means that when ASMR is used, companies can engage with and keep the audience's attention for longer than traditionally voiced audio ads.

In the last 5 or 6 years, researchers have begun to investigate the physiologic and psychologic traits associated with ASMR. Studies are emerging from various countries like China, Japan, Iran, Finland, Poland, and the United States, pointing to the global growth of interest amongst scientists. Among those trailblazers to make a scientific enquiry is Dr. Craig Richard who launched “ASMR University” (n.d.), a comprehensive resource for students, scholars, and enthusiasts to follow blogs, learn about the latest research, and learn how to be a “ASMRtist” (ASMR content creator or ASMR artist).

Pedrini et al. (2021) examined for changes in pupillary diameter and arousal level among 76 participants who watched a 30 second clip of a video with ASMR content, and control video without ASMR content. Their results essentially showed that pupil dilation is the largest with ASMR content videos. They also found that delta values on EEG during the ASMR video were lower than during the High-Arousal, Low-Arousal and Control videos. Theta values during the

ASMR video were lower than during the Low-Arousal and Control videos. Alpha Delta appeared lower during the ASMR video than during the Low-Arousal and Control videos. Low Beta values were lower during the ASMR video than during the High-Arousal, Low-Arousal, and Control videos. ASMR experiencers showed reduced functional connectivity (the coactivation of brain regions over time) in a number of areas of the Default Mode Network (DMN; a large-scale neural network comprising the angular gyri, posterior cingulate, and medial prefrontal cortices). The DMN has been linked with internal mentation and self-referential processing, and with observing highly moving and emotional artwork.

As a follow up to an fMRI study, Reddy and Mohabbat (2020) repeated a similar experiment and reported that ASMR and frisson showed similar neurofunctional patterns. Activation occurred in the nucleus accumbens, dorsal anterior cingulate cortex, supplementary motor area, and insula, which are associated reward and emotion. Moreover, people with ASMR had increased activation of the medial prefrontal cortex, an area associated with social cognition, social behaviors (i.e. grooming), and self-awareness, while people with frisson had reduced activation of this area.

Objective

This thesis consists of 2-parts: a systematic review of current publications on therapeutic use of ASMR, and a within-subjects auditory training trial using ASMR videos. The main intent is to explore the therapeutic benefit for those with atypical sensory processing. A focus on atypical sensory processing was elected to examine a slightly broader range than hearing impairment alone, due to research of ASMR still budding. Many hearing-related, mood or anxiety symptoms overlap with symptoms of sensory processing issues. Symptoms more unique to hearing disorders are expanded upon in the next few paragraphs. Inclusion and exclusion

criteria of the systematic review were developed in order to produce optimal search outcomes, and avoid overly confined criteria that would limit yielded results.

The STAR Institute of Colorado (n.d.) provides a succinct purview of subtypes of atypical sensory processing in Figure 1.

Atypical sensory processing symptoms include:

Hyperreactive: acutely aware of certain sounds and might feel as if they are being constantly bombarded with information. Often have a “fight or flight” response to sensation such as being touched unexpectedly or an unexpected loud noise (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Hyporeactive: may appear withdrawn or difficult to engage; may seem self-absorbed because they do not readily detect sensory input from their environment. Prone to clumsiness due to body movements and low responsiveness to tactile or deep pressure input (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Sensory craving: seem to have insatiable desire for sensory input by constantly moving, bumping, or jumping. They “need” to touch everything or be overly affectionate. Polar opposite of hyperreactive people who tend to avoid certain stimuli (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Postural: difficulty stabilizing the body during movement or at rest, in order to meet the demands of the environment or demands of a motor task (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Dyspraxia: difficulty planning and carrying out new motor actions, forming a goal, idea, or sequence of actions. Are clumsy and accident prone (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Sensory discrimination: problems determining the characteristics of sensory stimuli resulting in poor ability to interpret specific qualities of stimuli or difficulty detecting similarities and differences between textures or surfaces of objects (Mago, n.d.; Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.).

Abnormal hearing conditions that overlap in part with atypical sensory processing:

Recruitment: perception of sounds becoming rapidly louder with increasing sound level, often characterized by people with cochlear disorders asking others “to speak louder” followed by the complaint to “stop shouting” (Cai, Ma, and Young, 2009). Perceived overamplification of environmental sounds is the 3rd most common reason for hearing aid dissatisfaction (Sherlock and Fomby, 2017).

Hyperacusis: physical discomfort induced by exposure to light and/or a slightly loud sound with a sound pressure level not capable or likely to cause acoustic trauma (Science Direct, n.d.). Hyperacusis is found in Depression, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder, and Benzodiazepine dependence. There is a disturbance in the serotonergic system which modulates neuronal habituation responses to repetitive stimulation.

Musical ear syndrome: causes patients with hearing impairment to have non-psychiatric auditory hallucinations. In advanced age, it could be confused with dementia. Although its mechanism is unknown, secondary to hearing loss, phantom sounds are thought to be caused by hypersensitivity in the auditory cortex associated with sensory deprivation (Cakmak et al., 2016).

Misophonia: extreme aversiveness to specific sounds like chewing and sniffing. Each person will have their own unique set of triggers, which may include specific visual stimuli like leg swinging. It seems that the meaning, social context, or interpretation of

the trigger influences the response to these noises, distinguishes misophonia from other conditions like tinnitus, hyperacusis, and phonophobia (Rouw and Erfanian, 2017). A mechanism proposed to underlie misophonia is increased functional connectivity between the auditory and the limbic system, and abnormal functioning of the anterior insula cortex. An association had been noted between misophonic behavior and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, Attention Deficit Disorder, and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder.

Tinnitus: commonly described as a ringing, roaring, buzzing, cicadas, or crickets sound when there is no external sound source present. Tinnitus can occur when damage to the inner ear changes the signal carried by nerves to auditory cortex. Abnormal interactions between the auditory cortex and other neural circuits may play a role in tinnitus. Some people with tinnitus have changes in these nonauditory brain regions, like the limbic system (National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders, n.d.).

Central Auditory Processing Disorder: deficits in the neural processing of auditory information due to cerebral lesions as opposed to cochlear lesions (American Speech Language Hearing Association, n.d.) In a study of 2,791 students, those with mild hearing loss, had listening difficulties stemming from abnormal auditory processing (Ahn et al., 2020).

Introduction: Why is ASMR Auditory Training of interest?

The average person with difficulty hearing waits seven years before pursuing hearing aids, after clinically diagnosed with hearing loss. Mark Ross, the founding father of aural rehabilitation, reflected on that long wait: “Think about those years. Think about the effects these hearing problems may have had upon the person’s family, social circle, and employment situation. (Vandenhoff, 2023).” Over the period of delayed hearing aid selection, a person

subconsciously adjusts to the hearing deficiency. For example, they stop watching TV with a significant other because the volume is too loud. Hearing aids can solve the problem of a too-loud TV—but hearing aids alone are not a perfect solution in and of themselves.

During communication activities, the listener's brain processes incoming sounds to try understanding what was heard (MED-EL, 2022). However, the brain must work harder to if hearing loss is present and this greater workload requires the allocation of resources normally assigned to other activities such as learning and committing what is heard to memory. The reduced auditory working memory over the long-term is associated with other comorbidities.

For instance, a literature review reported that visual impairment, mobility restrictions, cognitive impairment, psychosocial health problems, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, arthritis, and cancer (treated with chemo) all had larger prevalence in people with a hearing loss. Risk of falling was greater in the hearing impaired, particularly if co-existing with vision impairment. Hearing loss was reported to be associated with 12% higher prevalence of anxiety per 10 dB increase in pure tone thresholds. Hearing aid use was not associated with lower ratios of anxiety, but was associated with social and emotional loneliness, and increased risk for depression (Besser et al., 2018). Deal et al. (2019) found data drawing similar conclusions about hearing loss comorbidities. VA Medical Center claims for services rendered between January 2000 and December 2016 revealed that hearing loss was significantly associated with an increased 10-year risk of dementia, depression, falls, and myocardial infarction.

After provision of hearing technology, such as hearing aids or cochlear implants, the newly improved sound detection ability will need to be accompanied with auditory training to rehabilitate the auditory working memory capacity. The following several paragraphs explore some strengths and weaknesses of various auditory training methods used in the industry.

A pilot study in Melbourne, Australia, was conducted to assess and compare outcomes of groups with aided and unaided auditory training regimen. Participants received 6 months of auditory training sessions in the form of speech tracking and an additional 3 months of only hearing aids. Hearing aid use reduced problems with communication, but there were no significant improvements in speech perception, social interaction or cognition (Nkyekyer et al., 2019). Depressive symptoms were significantly improved when treatment combined hearing aids with auditory training. There was a significant immediate improvement when hearing aids were first fitted for new users. Aversiveness of sound was significantly reduced when hearing aids were worn.

A systematic review that screened 229 articles published since 1996 is congruent to the above pilot study. Trained word-recognition performance was noted to improve from baseline of 37.6% to 83.5% immediately after training, and reduced to 62.9% six months after training (Henshaw and Ferguson, 2013). Participants improved on untrained word recognition by an average of 6.9%. Average improvement in measures of untrained speech intelligibility in people with hearing loss ranged from 3.3% for sentences, to 14.9% for words.

In another study said to be ongoing, participants completed 30 hours of training sessions with monaurally presented, spectrally shaped stimuli or through loudspeakers with their own hearing aids (Dubno, 2013). Open-set recognition of trained sounds, words, phrases, and sentences was significantly improved. Generalization varied between individuals for skills with the speech-perception task, competing noise, listening strategy, and pretraining scores.

Michaud et al.'s systematic review (2017) expands on the investigation of the efficacy of auditory training. Auditory training methods used in the articles included a combination of: orientation to hearing aid use, education about hearing assistive devices, speech-reading training,

syllable drills, synthetic exercises of sentence and paragraph length, communication strategies training, psychosocial exercises, practicing hearing tactics, coping strategies with loud noises, communication repair strategies, cognitive skills, problem solving skills, individualized behavioral counseling, identification of individual problem areas and setting goals, role play, active listening skills, video self-modeling, applied relaxation and completing homework between in-office check-ups. Measures of optimism did not show a treatment effect. Measures of emotional distress and discomfort, social withdrawal, participation restrictions, communication activity limitations, and general well-being, improved. Psychosocial exercises that focused on discussing problems, feelings, attitudes, emotions associated with hearing loss, and the impact of hearing loss on personal and professional relationships resulted in a reduction in hearing handicap. A computer-based game format resulted in small unremarkable improvements in measures of participants' ability to participate in different listening situations. Confidence building through the development of good listening habits resulted in decreased self-perception of hearing handicap. Structured syllable drills showed no treatment effect in terms of self-perceived hearing handicap. Active listening training had a significant impact on patients' awareness of communication difficulties, attitudes, effectiveness of communication strategies used, and acceptance and adjustment to hearing loss.

An intervention group that received at-home auditory training was compared with an active control group that listened to audiobooks at home, and a passive control group that wore hearing aids and completed no training activities (Humes et al., 2019). Outcome measures were obtained after a 5-week period. Participants who received the at-home training demonstrated significant improvements on aided recognition for trained materials, but no generalization of these benefits to nontrained materials was seen. This was despite reasonably good compliance

with the at-home training regimen and careful verification of hearing aid function throughout the trial. Based on follow-up post-trial evaluation, the gained progress of training was sustained for another 8.5 months.

A computer-based program called LACE (Listening and Communication Enhancement) was administered to 279 new and experienced hearing aid users, who completed 10 to 20 training sessions or listened to 10 hours of an audio book. Findings showed no significant improvements from the LACE program compared with standard-of-care hearing aid intervention alone (Saunders et al., 2016).

A computer-based program called cLEAR incorporated recordings of the voice of each participant's frequent communication partner. Participants, which included 10 couples, completed 12 hours of auditory training over the course of 6 weeks (Tye-Murray et al., 2016). Responses on the Client Oriented Scale of Improvement (COSI) indicated that training reduced participants' communication difficulties. On average, participants improved by 6.3%. The overall process of developing the program for each couple took about 20 hours of editing for the laboratory staff to do. For this reason, it would not be feasible to implement this method of program design for the general patient population.

An auditory training program using a closed-loop sensorimotor interface in a video game format was administered to elderly hearing-impaired subjects, who had already been using bilateral hearing aids an average of 7 years (Whitton et al., 2017). They conducted training for approximately 3.5 hours per week for 8 weeks, and the program required them to monitor subtle deviations between predicted and actual auditory feedback as they moved their fingertip through a virtual soundscape. Post-training outcome measures showed they could correctly identify an average of 25% more words in spoken sentences or digit sequences with background

noise. These gains did not persist when tested in the absence of further intervention 2 months later.

Premise for Developing the ASMR Auditory Training Trial

ASMR involves both visceral and emotional responses to a stimulus, as identified by an fMRI study. The researchers examined activation of various brain regions: the central executive network (CEN) which is involved with attentional set shifting, response inhibition, working memory, and problem solving; and the salience network (SN) which is sensitive to visceral feedback from the body. (Smith et al., 2019). The SN showed stronger, more coherent functional connectivity in control participants than in individuals with ASMR; there was also a link between auditory perception and salience judgments. Control participants had greater functional connectivity in many motoric areas, whereas individuals experiencing ASMR showed increased connectivity in the primary somatosensory cortex as well as regions related to emotion and reward responses (i.e., the amygdala and orbital gyrus). Because emotions often play a part in the decision to seek hearing loss treatment, and providers could piggyback on this by incorporating an Auditory Rehabilitation program that ties into positive emotions from ASMR.

Tye-Murray et al. (2012) reported that despite 88% of their participants experiencing improvement in at least one aspect of speech comprehension after the auditory training program, none of the measures of perceived benefit correlated with overall program enjoyment. Their findings suggest that the perceived benefit of auditory training did not contribute to an individual's enjoyment of the program. A total of 20% of participants felt the program was tedious/boring/monotonous/fatiguing. In addition, 10% said they disliked completing the program in a clinical setting, and another 10% cited recurring transportation and appointment scheduling obligations were an unfavorable factor of the program. Yet, 19% liked having

consistent contact with a hearing care provider throughout the program despite the aforementioned obligations.

Hoare et al. (2014) enrolled 60 participants in either a conventional task-based auditory training, or interactive game-style training platform for six weeks. Participants reported greater intrinsic motivation to train on the interactive game-style platform. A reported actual compliance rate of 70%, and the above study where 20% of participants were bored, reveals some kind of cognitive dissonance. Perhaps a social driving force to be amiable causes patients to verbally agree with their hearing care provider's prescribed treatment plans, only to lack true follow-through when no longer in the presence of their provider. Perhaps there are subtle cues that the hearing care provider can do better at detecting, in order to personalize the treatment regimen while also saving face.

When considering people's desire for convenient access to training programs, Olson (2015) used multiple search engines to determine mobile program accessibility. Their search yielded a total of 127 auditory training apps for iPhone, iPad, Macintosh, and Android systems. No app included evidence-based research to support its actual use. Many programs allow clients to train at home at their leisure and are self-directed, while others require clinician-directed training. Some programs provide training through auditory stimuli only, or both auditory and visual cues. Programs varied in availability of language, cost, targeted auditory skills, type of stimuli, and the number of speakers used during training. Several were not actually usable when reviewers tried to open and operate them. Furthermore, several apps had limited or no reviews, or had not been updated in several years.

Some hearing technology manufacturers like Cochlear Americas (n.d.), Advanced Bionics (n.d.), and MED-EL (n.d.) offer self-directed auditory training programs accessed

through their own websites or apps. As noted about some apps above, a guided tutorial from a hearing care professional or manufacturer's representative would be beneficial for a patient that is not tech savvy when navigating the manufacturers' websites.

Spehar et al. (2015) compared the use of sentence based and situation based contextual cues presented either with an image only or with audio only. For instance, a phrase would be presented with a single picture as its clue, or a phrase with clues referencing a particular scenario would be presented. Participants received more benefit when the sentence-based and situation-based clues occurred in the visual-only modality than when it occurred in the auditory-only modality. Overall, the report suggests that aural rehabilitation programs might provide training to optimize use of both kinds of contextual cues.

Developing any training program for adult participants necessitates a review of some essential items. According to Leib (1991), at least six factors serve as sources of motivation for adult learning:

- Social relationships: make and maintain friendships.
- External expectations: comply with recommendations from someone else
- Social welfare: improve ability to serve the community
- Personal advancement: job promotion/higher status/competitive advantage
- Escape/Stimulation: relieve boredom, provide a break from daily routines
- Cognitive interest: learn for the sake of learning/satisfy an inquiring mind
- Positive reinforcement: see a reward/demonstrated benefit from learning
- Relevant: applicable to their work, goals, or other responsibilities

Part 1: Systematic Literature Review

Several search engines were used including PubMed, PLOS One, Web of Science, Academia, ClinicalTrials.gov. Search terms used included “ASMR”, “ASMR therapy”, “ASMR treatment”, “ASMR therapeutic”, and “ASMR health”. The bibliography cited within articles also served as search material. A total of 1,088 publications were found.

Criteria for inclusion in this review are: (1) adult participants diagnosed with hearing loss or atypical sensory processing, (2) inclusion of measures related to ASMR as a treatment method and (3) published between 2000 and 2022. The researcher screened each search result page for relevant articles by titles first, then screened by abstract, and lastly narrowed them down by more comprehensive review of the experimental design, data collected, and intervention effect reported.

Part 1 Results

A total of 13 articles met inclusion criteria, as discussed below. Table 1 summarizes them by sample/design, treatment, outcome, and data quality. Further details about the individual reports are discussed thereafter.

Table 1

ASMR Therapy Report Summary Table

Reference	Sample/Design/Variables	Treatment	Outcome	Data Quality
Poerio et al., 2018	N=1002; within-subjects design; control stimuli used Heart Rate (HR) Skin Conductance (SC) Questionnaire on presence of tingles and relaxation	3 videos (2 with ASMR, 1 without ASMR)	Greater degree of triggers with sound based and speech based ASMR compared with control Greater reduced HR in triggered vs non-triggered Greater increased SC in triggered vs non-triggered	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Sakurai et al., 2021	N=30; within-subjects design fMRI	Classical music and ASMR music	Greater activation of left calcarine cortex, right superior frontal gyrus medial segment,	Outcomes based on objective

	Questionnaire on presence of frisson vs ASMR, and mood		right lingual gyrus, and medial prefrontal cortex (dopamine/oxytocin/relaxation regions) with ASMR music No respondents reported experience of frisson or somatic symptoms with ASM	data and self-report
Barratt and Davis, 2015	N=475; within-subjects design Qualtrics survey version 36,892 with Lickert style questions on mood, relaxation, stress, and chronic pain; Beck Depression Index (BDI)	ASMR videos (known 22length)	Average 78 out of 100 BDI grade for improved mood 50% improved mood despite no tingles triggered 98% improved relaxation 82% better sleep 70% improved stress 38 out of 475 improved chronic pain 40 out of 475 reported no improvement in chronic pain	Outcomes based on self-report
Engelbregt et al., 2022	N=38; between-subjects design; control group used Shortened Profile of Mood States (POMS); Heart rate (HR); Electrodermal activity (EDA); Electroencephalography (EEG) Mann-Whitney test	2 ASMR videos (length?)	Depression scores decreased No significant difference in Anger, Fatigue, Vigor, & Tension compared with non-triggered group HR reduced for triggered and non-triggered during ASMR stimulus EDA unchanged Increased Beta on EEG for triggered and non-triggered groups	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Smejka and Wiggs, 2022	N=1,037; within-subjects design Questionnaires on insomnia, mood, and depression	1 ASMR video (length?)	Increased relaxation Improved mood No difference between the insomnia and depression groups	Outcomes based on self-report
Eid et al., 2022	N=64; between-subjects design State versus Trait Anxiety; Major Depressive Disorder	5-minute ASMR video	Attenuated State Anxiety for ASMR triggered, no difference for non-triggered	Outcomes based on self-report
Hu et al., 2022	N=122; between-subjects design; control group used Addiction Stroop Task State Anxiety Inventory; Trait Anxiety Inventory;	59 ASMR videos, 1 to 3 minutes long, every 2 to 3 days for 12 weeks	Decreased state anxiety in experiment group Decreased Stroop Task reaction time No significant change in control group	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report

Seifzadeh et al., 2021	N=10; between-subjects design Heart Rate (HR) Galvanic Skin Conductance (GSC)	1 session of a 20-minute ASMR video	HR decreased in ASMR triggered group GSC reduced in ASMR triggered group	Outcomes based on objective data
Morales et al., 2021	N=176; between-subjects design Spanish Emotion Regulation Questionnaire on suppression, appraisal, reappraisal, and cognitive appraisal	ASMR videos (unknown duration)	Greater increase of cognitive reappraisal in ASMR triggered group than non-triggered group No difference between groups in expressive suppression	Outcomes based on self-report
Rouw and Erfanian, 2017	N=301; within-subjects design Qualtrics survey questions on misophonia reaction	ASMR sound (unknown duration)	Increased positive emotional association with ASMR trigger sounds Unchanged negative emotional association with misophonic trigger sounds	Outcomes based on self-report
Lee et al., 2019	N=15; within-subjects design Electroencephalogram (EEG) to assess sleep state Survey Questionnaire on emotional states	Binaural beat combined with ASMR triggers at 3 different binaural beat-to-ASMR sound level ratios	Greatest increase of Theta power and greatest decrease of Alpha power at 30:60dB ratio compared with 20:60dB & 45:60dB	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Paszkiew, et al., 2020	N=9; within-subjects design; control stimuli used Survey Questionnaire on stress level Heart Rate (HR) Blood Pressure (BP) Electroencephalogram (EEG)	4 sessions of 4 different stimuli on 4 different days (silence, rap, relaxing music, ASMR triggering music)	Rap music negatively affects stress level compared with silence (control) Relaxing music and ASMR music calms subjects faster than silence (control) ASMR music slightly more effective than relaxing music for relaxation Rap music not significantly different than silence in Alpha waves on EEG Both music genres significantly different than silence in Alpha waves on EEG Silence and Relaxing music greater reduction in HR and BP than the other stimuli	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Ditchburn and Bedwell, 2019	N=110; between-group design; control group used Zung's Self Rating Anxiety Scale; CESD-R Scale for depression;	1 ASMR video 1 to 2 hours before bed for 7 evenings (10 to 30-minute duration);	Significantly higher well-being scores with mindfulness than the control and ASMR Significantly decreased depression scores on all interventions	Outcomes based on self-report

	Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale ASMR Checklist for test condition trigger selection	Mindfulness practice intervention	Reduced anxiety in all 3 groups, largest reduction in anxiety scores with mindfulness compared with control group	
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Poerio et al. (2018) examined whether ASMR is associated with a pattern of physiology indicative of relaxation. The researcher systematically tested whether watching ASMR videos produce tingling and pleasant affect and objective physiological changes in heart rate and skin conductance. Participants watched a subset of three videos (two ASMR; one control) and then reported if they experienced tingling sensations. Soft speaking, hair play/brushing, whispering, and close personal attention were the most commonly reported tingle-triggers (reported by >65% of the 1002 participants). ASMR participants reported tingling sensations more frequently than non-ASMR participants to the sound-based and spoken-based ASMR videos; but less so to the control videos. The majority of the sample (83%) reported watching ASMR videos to trigger their ASMR, and over half (51%) reported watching videos daily or several times a week. Participants who experienced tingles showed significantly greater reductions in heart rate after watching both ASMR videos. Those who experienced ASMR trigger showed significantly greater increases in skin conductance after watching both types of ASMR videos, compared to non-triggered participants.

Sakurai et al (2021) conducted fMRI exams on 30 healthy subjects while they listened to ASMR and classical music, and compared the differences in brain activation associated with the 2 stimulations. Before the experiment, the subjects selected from 10 options of ASMR content that they liked the most and found most relaxing. The researchers selected Eine kleine Nachtmusik, a piece of music by Mozart. After the experiment the subjects were given a questionnaire on somatosensation and mood. Somatic symptoms include: nausea, jitteriness,

impatience, trembling, hypervigilance, sweating, palpitation, and faintness. Results of the questionnaire showed that none of the subjects experienced somatosensation during ASMR stimulation; furthermore, none of the subjects experienced musical frisson. Significant activation was observed in the left calcarine cortex, right superior frontal gyrus medial segment, and right lingual gyrus during ASMR stimulation compared to classical music. Both classical music and ASMR produced a pleasant and relaxed state, and ASMR involved more complex brain functions than classical music, especially of the medial prefrontal cortex. ASMR stimulation is thought to be more effective in inducing relaxation and reducing stress than classical music because it involves brain regions associated with these functions (i.e. the dopamine and oxytocin pathways).

Barratt and Davis (2015) surveyed 475 participants via an online questionnaire in order to gather information about the benefits individuals receive from ASMR. Participants were asked to report whether or not they experienced any of the triggers in a list of 9 given stimuli: crisp sounds, whispering, personal attention, vacuum noise, airplane noise, laughing, smiling, watching repetitive tasks, and slow movements. Of these suggestions, five sounds to most likely trigger ASMR (i.e. close personal attention, crisp sounds) and 4 sounds least likely to trigger ASMR were identified (i.e. vacuum noise, airplane noise, laughing, smiling). A total of 98% of participants achieved relaxation with ASMR videos. In a similar vein, 82% reported that ASMR helped them sleep, and 70% reported that ASMR helped them cope with stress. Participants reportedly felt best while they are engaging with ASMR media, with reports on the 0 to 100 scale of positive mood averaging at 78 for this time period. The effect on mood steadily decreased over the course of several hours. There was also a correlation between BDI (Beck Depression Index) scores and the difference in mood score between baseline and immediately after an

ASMR experience, suggesting that people with higher depression scores had the greatest benefit from engaging in ASMR. Moreover, 50% of participants said their mood improved even in sessions when no tingling sensation was triggered, while 30% said that achieving this sensation was vital to mood improvement. Only 38 individuals reported that ASMR improved their chronic pain symptoms. Lastly, 40 individuals did not believe that ASMR had an impact on their chronic pain.

Engelbregt (2022) examined the effects of an ASMR video on mood, attention, heart rate (HR), electrodermal activity (EDA), electroencephalography (EEG) and the interaction with personality factors in 38 young adults. Mood was measured by the Profile of Mood States (Anger, Depression, Tension, Fatigue and Vigor). Participants were only told that the aim of the study was to examine the effects of different types of videos on mood, attention, heart rate, skin conductance and EEG. After all participants had watched the same two videos in a counterbalanced order, they were assigned to the ASMR and non-ASMR group. A total of 15 out of 38 participants were classified as ASMR-experiencers. The scores of Depression decreased under the ASMR condition as compared to the control condition in the ‘tingles group’ relative to the ‘no tingles group’, but not significantly. Mann–Whitney test did not indicate a significant difference in Depression score between Tingles and No-tingles group under the control condition. There were no significant differences between Groups for Anger, Fatigue, Vigor and Tension. With respect to EEG, an increase of beta power in the left temporal area was found in the whole group of participants irrespective of ASMR-sensitivity after watching an ASMR video. This increase may reflect improved focused attention due to associated with beta activity which is known to also increase during meditation.

Smieka and Wiggs (2022) collected online questionnaires from 1,037 participants which assessed insomnia and depression symptom severity. Additional questionnaires on current mood and arousal levels were collected before and after watching an ASMR video. All participants showed significantly increased relaxation and improved mood after watching the video with the largest effects for participants who experienced ASMR and for participants in the combined and depression groups. No difference was found between the insomnia and control groups. The report indicated that the link between insomnia and depression is well established in the literature; management plans for depression often include treatment components to tackle insomnia, and intervention is more successful when both problems are addressed. Insomnia improvement may mediate the improvement in depressive symptoms (Smeika and Wiggs, 2022).

Eid et al. (2022) assessed levels of neuroticism, trait anxiety, and pre-/post- ASMR video state anxiety among 36 ASMR-experiencers and 28 non-experiencers. ASMR-experiencers had significantly greater baseline scores for neuroticism, trait anxiety, and video engagement than non-experiencers. Pre-video state anxiety was also significantly greater in the ASMR-experiencers and was significantly attenuated on exposure to the ASMR video, whereas non-experiencers reported no difference in state anxiety pre- and post-video. Thus, watching ASMR alleviated state anxiety (level of moment to moment anxiety) versus trait anxiety (stable and enduring tendency to experience anxiety), but only in those who experienced ASMR. Notably, a significant number of those who are capable of experiencing ASMR suffer from Major Depressive Disorder. The report found that neuroticism, pre-video state anxiety, and video engagement each acted as significant mediators, resulting in the relationship between Group and change in state anxiety being rendered non-significant. Therefore, the researchers questioned

whether ASMR could be considered as an intervention for those with elevated neuroticism and anxiety, but do not actively watch ASMR videos or have not experienced ASMR tingles.

Hu et al. (2022) recruited about 122 female substance abuse detoxification patients. Except for the 12-week training of ASMR, the experimental conditions of the experimental group (n = 60) were the same as those of the control group (n = 62). The addiction Stroop task was used to assess the level of psychological cravings and the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory was used to assess the level of anxiety. The experimental group had a greater decrease in state anxiety, as well as reduced reaction time on Stroop Task, than the control group. The reduction in reaction time is reported to be significant because of the association for impulsive, uncontrollable, drug cravings with attentional bias. Attentional bias can cause addicts to skew their attention—subconscious over attention is paid to cues related to addictive substances, and creates a vicious circle of detoxification and relapse. The higher the addicts' attentional bias toward drug-related cues, the worse their Stroop task performance. Videos containing ASMR triggers from a validated video library were selected, comprising 59 videos. The length of each video was between one and three minutes. State anxiety (SAI) scores of the two groups were not significantly different about 1 month after onset of the training, but significantly lower (improved) at 6 weeks. Researchers concluded that ASMR could thus reduce to a certain extent the state anxiety and attentional bias for drug-related clues underlying psychological cravings among women compulsorily isolated for detoxification.

Morales et al. (2021) investigated individual differences in emotion regulation mechanisms by studying suppression and reappraisal behaviors with relation to ASMR, using a validated Spanish version of the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire. Suppression refers to when an ongoing emotion-expressive behavior becomes inhibited. Reappraisal is defined in the article

as a cognitive reevaluation of the emotionally arousing situation to alter its emotional impact. Cognitive reappraisal involves the person's attempts to change the emotional impact by changing how they think of the situation. Expressive suppression refers to the person's attempts to hide or inhibit the expression of their emotions. The experimental sample consisted of 108 Spanish speaking participants who reported being ASMR-triggered and 68 participants not being triggered. The ASMR group showed significantly higher scores in cognitive reappraisal than the non-ASMR group. There were no significant differences between ASMR and non-ASMR groups for expressive suppression. The greater use of cognitive reevaluation suggests more effective emotion regulation. The study confirmed that ASMR is a legitimate psychophysiological phenomenon associated with other psychological constructs and has remarkable consequences in affective/emotional dimensions and general well-being.

Seifzadeh et al. (2021) had 10 participants watch 20 minutes of a Mixed-ASMR video including the combination of the most popular and the most effective triggers, to find out how ASMR could be relaxing and efficient as an immediate outlet for anxiety in solely one session. The researchers examined the physiological bases of anxiety such as heart rate and skin conductance to prove anxiety reduction. Subjects were attached to a digital sampling unit for the autonomic system polygraph. By this, real-time Galvanic Skin Conductance and Heart Rate were recorded. The results indicated that the heart rate decreased significantly in the ASMR group. Compared to baseline, there is a significant decline in the post-test. A slightly reduced skin conductance was observed after watching the video, but it was not significant.

Rouw and Erfanian (2017) surveyed personal, developmental, and clinical characteristics of over 300 participants with misophonia, and its relation to ASMR. The online experiment comprised 55 items, including yes/no questions, multiple answer questions, and open-ended

questions. Participants were asked about a variety of categories: demographic characteristics; age of onset of their misophonic responses; if/when the participant received a misophonia diagnosis; auditory triggers; possible changes in triggers over time, family history of misophonia and other conditions or disorders; coping strategies; effects of substances on misophonic responses; emotional and physical properties of their misophonic responses; visual triggers; possible presence of synesthesia; possible comorbid conditions; possible experience of ASMR; provoked thoughts during a misophonic reaction; and the impact misophonia had on their life. The most common physical complaint for misophonics on pre-ASMR intake was: “I feel physical sensation which can be best described as emotional pain.” A total of 20% of the participants indicated that “thoughts of suicide” is one of the effects that misophonia has on their life. In addition, 49% of the participants indicated experiencing a euphoric relaxing tingle in response to ASMR content. This shows that misophonia symptoms were abated in nearly half of the participants after listening to specific sounds like ASMR on regular basis. Results also showed that ASMR adds positive emotions to the scale of sound-induced emotions, but does not significantly decrease the negative effects of misophonia.

Paskiel et al. (2020) analyzed the therapeutic impact of various combinations of music and ASMR on stress level in subjects. The conducted experiment involved nine females. All participants were healthy and did not have any neurological or psychiatric disorders. The test included four types of audio stimuli: silence (control sample), rap, relaxing music and music triggering an autonomous sensory meridian response (ASMR). The duration of this experiment was 4 days, with the type of sound stimulation replaced each successive day by another musical genre, with the rest of the testing remaining the same. At specific stages, the blood pressure and pulse was measured, and participants completed a questionnaire. Throughout the entire

experiment, the EEG was monitored for the presence of alpha-waves. The relaxing and ASMR music genres reduced autonomic symptoms of stress, subject also reached a calmer state than before the stressor. Relaxing music was somewhat worse, however statistical analysis shows no significant difference compared with ASMR music. Both ASMR-triggering and relaxing music showed significant difference compared to silence for the magnitude of the alpha waves. Rap music, on the other hand, showed no significant difference compared to silence in alpha waves. The study concluded that rap music negatively affects the reduction of stress level compared to the control group, while relaxing music and ASMR calms subjects much faster than silence.

Ditchburn and Bedwell (2019) posit that based on data, ASMR is not a reliable form of long-term therapy. Data was collected using three separate questionnaires before and after an eight-day intervention. Validated anxiety, depression, and well-being scales were used. A total of 110 participants were randomly assigned to one of 2 test conditions, and a control group. For one test condition, participants watched 10 to 30 minutes of ASMR videos via YouTube for 7 consecutive nights 1 to 2 hours before bed. Mindfulness themes were utilized for the second test condition. ASMR triggers were selected using an ASMR checklist and popular triggers identified in ASMR forums. The control group did not watch any videos. On day eight, all participants completed the three psychometric tests. Results found a significant decrease in post-intervention scores across all three interventions for depression, with no significant difference between groups. Results revealed that average decrease in anxiety was greatest for the mindfulness group. Well-being scores improved for both intervention types. The study noted while ASMR was not significantly different than mindfulness in improving symptoms of anxiety, depression, and well-being, there was doubt about its long-term effect post-intervention, due to the short timeframe of the intervention administered.

Lee et al. (2019) used a 6 Hz binaural beat with the theta band (4 to 8 Hz) at various combinations of ASMR as an auditory stimulus to mimic the non-rapid eye movement of stage 1 sleep. They investigated which combination could most effectively induce sleep, based on questionnaires and EEG measures. The auditory stimulations included binaural beat alone, ASMR trigger alone, silence as the control stimulation, ratio of binaural beats-to-ASMR of 45:60, ratio of binaural beats-to-ASMR of 30:60, and ratio of binaural beats-to-ASMR of 20:60. A total of 15 subjects underwent all stimulations. Subjects' questionnaire responses showed reduction in anger, tension, depression, and confusion in each stimulation ratio, as well as reduced vigor. The scores in happiness were most significantly increased in the 30:60 stimulation ratio. Calmness was significantly lower in the 45:60 stimulation ratio compared with the 30:60 and 20:60 ratios. EEGs showed significantly reduced theta power in all stimulation ratios, while alpha power was reduced in all but the silence stimulation. Beta power was significantly reduced in the combined stimulations compared with binaural beats alone, ASMR alone, and silence. It is thought that when binaural beats induce desired oscillations of the auditory and sensory neural pathways, the thalamus's role in promoting sleep can be optimized. ASMR can have an indirect therapeutic benefit for people with chronic tinnitus and comorbidity of insomnia (Wiseloge, 2022).

Part 2: Participants for the Trial

Those eligible to participate were at least 18 years old, had self-reported normal or corrected vision, had access to YouTube from a personal electronic device with a loud speaker either embedded or connected to the device, and had a self-reported perceived or diagnosed hearing impairment. Participants were not required to know what ASMR is, nor had prior ASMR triggers. Invitations to recruit participants were posted in 5 Facebook groups, 1 Reddit forum,

and 7 LinkedIn groups dedicated to people with hearing impairment and hearing care professionals. Invitation letters were mailed to 30 hearing care and family medicine clinics within a 15-mile radius of the author's location, as determined by a search of Google Maps. The social media post and invitation letter are included in Appendices 4 and 5, respectively.

Participants started their trials on a rolling basis. Informed consent was obtained by way of the ASMR Auditory Training Program Guide (Appendix 2). The program guide informed participants of the voluntary nature of enrollment, of potential risks of unsafe listening volumes or unpleasant misophonia triggers, that all information was kept private, questionnaire responses collected anonymously, and of the university supervisors overseeing the project. The participants were not given any specific goals to pursue during the program, but were aware of the overall objective of exploring its use as Auditory Training. They were advised of Task 1 (to watch the ASMR videos), and given Task 2 (questionnaire) after reporting to the researcher they completed Task 1.

Part 2 Intervention Method and Materials

ASMR videos were selected from YouTube after a general review of search results using search terms like "ASMR nature sounds", "ASMR role play", and "ASMR word phonics". Titles were first screened based on title for topics comparable to the scripted closed-set words, phrases, and sounds in computer-based or app-based training programs such as Angel Sound (Emily Fu Foundation, n.d.), Games4Hearoes (n.d.), and SoundSuccess (Advanced Bionics, n.d.). Then, each video, totaling approximately 75 videos, was viewed by the researcher for the first 10 to 15 minutes to verify that the content was socially appropriate, relevant to the intended use, and to verify the visual and audio quality. Ultimately, a list of 27 ASMR videos were included in the ASMR Auditory Training Program Guide, to minimize the duration of each training session. The

program was distributed via a Google Drive Document link to participants' personal email accounts, as well as via the ASMR University website (Richard, n.d.). The 27 videos were split to 5 or 6 videos per training session, totaling 6 sessions over the course of 2 weeks. Due to many videos 1 or more hour long, participants were instructed to view the first 7 to 10 minutes of role play videos and the first 45 to 60 seconds of sound clip videos to minimize tediousness of sessions. Participants were advised to view the videos in a quiet space with comfortable lighting and the volume about the same level as a normal conversation.

After completing Task 1, participants were directed to a SurveyMonkey link to complete Task 2 (Appendix 1). One question split into 9 listening skills and asked to what degree the participants agreed that those listening skills were practiced during the video sessions (strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, strongly disagree). The auditory skills assessed in the questionnaire were derived from recommendations published by the American Speech Hearing Association (n.d.): pitch, intensity and phoneme discrimination, auditory signal sequencing, auditory pattern recognition, dichotic listening to separate fundamental speech sounds from background noise, sound localization, interhemispheric transfer (multimodal tasks such as linking prosodic and linguistic acoustic features, verbally describing an image while drawing, or interaural sound differentiation). Questions briefly inquired about the participants' hearing impairment status, use of hearing assistive technology, and preferred learning method. One question asked for suggestions on improving the ASMR Auditory Training Program in a free text response.

Part 2 Results

About 2 months after creating the video list, the link to a jackhammer sound clip video was inaccessible. It may have been taken down by the host site or video creator, or the link

domain may have been malfunctioning. This necessitated revision of the ASMR Auditory Training Program Guide to replace the original link with another ASMR jackhammer sound clip video. A link to the alternate video was then provided to the 2 participants who needed it at that time, and all other participants received the revised video list with no other issues.

The trial period that ran from January 2023 to May 2023; 30 individuals came forward expressing interest in enrolling. Ultimately, 13 people completed the training program and questionnaire. After enrolled, 10 participants were inactive throughout the trial period, by not responding to researcher's follow up emails to encourage continued training sessions. In addition, 7 opted out after completing only a small portion of the training program, and reasons given included unforeseen schedule conflicts impeding their ability to commit to completion, lack of compensation for time spent doing the tasks, and feeling overwhelmed by a perception that the task was more tedious than presumed. There was 1 response of "no" for the post-trial questionnaire, "Have you ever been formally diagnosed a hearing loss, or do you believing you have some degree of hearing loss?", despite all 30 people initially indicating, when asked by the researcher, if they have difficulty hearing during a significant amount of activities of daily living. It is possible that, despite an affirmative answer initially, the respondent misinterpreted this question as referring only if evaluated clinically.

A summary report of the post-trial questionnaire responses is available in Appendix 5. A total of 61.54% prefer self-paced online formats for listening skills training, compared with other formats as reflected in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1

Post-Trial Responses for Preferred Listening Skills Training Format

A majority of 64.29% agreed that the duration and amount of auditory training sessions was reasonable. Moreover, 71.43% agreed that the training improved their perception of music. Lastly, 64.29% agreed that the training improved their perception of a primary talker when there are other talkers or background noises present. All except 5 participants skipped the free-text space to provide suggestions on improving the ASMR auditory training program. A single participant reported tapping sounds in some videos to be potentially irritating, 2 reported improved relaxation, and 2 reported unsure if significant improvement (either due to the short trial or due to believing ASMR to be better intended as a relaxation activity rather than learning activity).

Due to the study design, treatment effect and between person metrics were not included in analysis of the post-trial questionnaire responses.

Discussion and Recommendations

There were several articles not cited here that, based on abstract alone, may have provided substantial contribution to this systematic review. However, the inclusion and exclusion criteria could not be appropriately applied to those due to controlled access. The abstract and summary background would be available to the general public, and full text only available to paid account holders of that journal or database. There were 3 occasions in which inquiries were sent to the editor of a scientific journal that published an article of interest, or to the author themselves if an email was posted on the site. No responses were received. It was not feasible to send additional inquiries for every inaccessible article. Moreover, some articles referenced within studies discussed in this paper were inaccessible due to the printed publication not attainable.

The World Health Organization estimates that by the year 2050 1 in 10 people will have disabling hearing loss (2023). That number is currently 1 in 4 for adults age 60 and up (2023). Of those prescribed hearing aids, 20-30% reject them for reasons including low perception of impact (correlated in part to level of awareness of degree of hearing loss), cost of treatment (access to care), and motivation (Marcos-Alonso et al., 2023). While subscription and view rates of ASMR channels in YouTube and Twitch are readily available, the total number of ASMR videos and channels is not attainable (Richard, n.d.). When searching for videos in a specific language, this yielded a mix of English-speaking “accents” from role-play videos as well as videos fluently using that language. For example, if searching “ASMR in German” or “ASMR Deutch” the video descriptions were either written in the German language or indicated that the performer would speak English with a “German accent”. Due to not fluent in German, the present researcher assumed that those written in German language were performed entirely in that

language. Therefore, it is not unreasonable to believe there are many videos available in at least the most common languages around the world, such as Spanish, French, Hindi, Mandarin, Russian, or Italian. This availability is significant due to the minimal findings of computer based or mobile app based Auditory Training programs in multiple languages. For hearing care providers that serve an ethnically and socio-economically diverse demographic of patients, ASMR videos from YouTube or Twitch (platforms that are free to the public) can be a viable component of treatment.

Recommendations for further research are proposed in tandem with recommendations by Hostler and Danielsson (2022). Their paper outlines five practices that ASMR researchers can use to improve the legitimacy of the field, accelerate the mobilization of the research community, and increase the transparency, rigor, and reproducibility of their research. Those practices are: pre-register with a review committee to publicly and transparently report a study's design and analysis plan prior to data collection, share raw data (de-identified in cases of human subjects), share study materials used, attain more adequate sample sizes via multi-lab collaboration, and post findings to open access repositories to permit empirical replicability studies.

Several limitations of the present ASMR Auditory Training trial have been identified, necessitating future repeat trials with enhanced experimental design. Those limitations include: no control group, reliance on self-report of hearing impairment from participants, and unable to objectively assess between-group treatment effect due to non-controlled test condition and no objective pre-trial measures collected. Many participants reside in another state or country; therefore, some objective measures like audiometric thresholds or speech recognition could not be obtained.

The future ASMR Auditory Training experimental design will be a controlled randomized between-groups study in which trial outcome data will account for aided, unaided, ASMR triggered, and non-ASMR triggered groups. The study would exclude those with clinically significant misophonia and clinically significant cognitive impairment. Baseline qualitative self-report measures using formats previously validated by prior researchers (Tinnitus and Hearing Survey, Hearing Handicap Inventory for Adults), along with post-trial self-report measures (Post-Trial ASMR Auditory Training Questionnaire, Tinnitus and Hearing Survey, Hearing Handicap Inventory for Adults) will be collected (Aeillo et al., 2011; Henry et al., 2015). A hearing aid function screening check list will be developed to verify the consistency of this condition among the aided group. Otoscopy will be performed, along with baseline and post-trial speech audiometry. Participants will be trained how to use a Sound Level Meter app to verify consistent listening volume and ambient noise level for all in-home auditory training sessions. ASMR videos will be implemented into the program using a validation process that Liu and Zhou completed (2019).

Some articles surmise that the efficacy of ASMR Auditory Training may diminish due to an apparent “ASMR immunity” (Poerio et al., 2018). This immunity supposedly occurs when the intensity of the tingles diminishes over time when trigger sounds are overused. Dr. Richard, researcher and author of “ASMR University” advises that, instead of immunity, it should be called tolerance. He indicated that if they stopped watching the videos for one or two weeks, the ASMR sensations normally return (Oxenham, 2016).

In reference to post-treatment effects reported by some to have reverted weeks or months after, it would be logical to say that patients would be best served long-term with periodic refresher auditory training after completing initial comprehensive intervention. But, this cannot

be suggested without also considering risks of learning delays from delayed intervention in pre-lingual hearing loss. Similarly, potential risks of sensory deprivation from delayed intervention in post-lingual hearing loss undermine realistic expectations for Auditory Training outcomes. Future research on comorbidities should also examine the association between risks like increased fall injuries and treated versus untreated hearing loss. Lastly, patients' success relies as much on the type of training program and lapse of time between diagnosis and treatment, as their own compliance. Henshaw and Ferguson indicated in their 2013 review that on average, participants completed 37 of the requested 44 days of training (92.5%), and reported overall compliance of 73%.

Many Auditory Training studies focused mostly on the listener. Often the burden is placed on the listener to correctly perceive every message. The listener is further worried when the speaker turned away from the listener, spoke while washing the dishes with the water running and the silverware clanking, or shouted from another region of the house. If the speaker fails to gain the listener's attention, does not wait until the listener is ready (for example, until they've turned down the television volume), is not within an adequate distance, or is not facing each other in the same room, then the message will not be accurately received (Laffan, 2021). Auditory training programs should be geared toward both the hearing-impaired patients and their frequent communication partners.

Conclusion

In summary, when considering the principles of adult learning, feedback from participants, and characteristics of various auditory training programs, hearing care providers can develop a well-rounded program to optimize their patients' hearing loss treatment outcomes. This is based on the comorbidities associated with hearing loss, typical negative compensatory

behaviors such as social withdrawal, and reported improvement in depression, focus, anxiety, stress, sense of achievement, and interpersonal openness among ASMR viewers. ASMR can be utilized for reacclimating to various sounds that may exacerbate symptoms of recruitment and rehabilitating the auditory working memory with a simulated social interaction. Sessions can be personalized for those with both hearing impairment and misophonia. People are generally already primed for computer based auditory training due to the convenience and increasingly common practice of telehealth. Hearing care providers can continuously engage with their patients via telecare throughout various stages of patients' auditory training regimen. The positive emotions invoked by the calm and happy nature of many ASMR videos could positively reinforce patients to comply with completing their training sessions. In the way that one hearing aid style is not the best choice for all patients, ASMR for auditory training is one of many methods that can be a component of treatment for those it benefits.

Project Approval

This thesis, particularly the research method and experiment design, has been evaluated and approved by the project tutor, Dr. Nerea Ortega Castro and the Director of SAERA, Dr. Joaquín Vidal López. There are no conflicts to report.

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Figures

Figure 1. *Sensory Processing Disorder Subtypes* (Star Institute for Sensory Processing, n.d.)

Tables

Table 1

ASMR Therapy Report Summary Table

Reference	Sample/Design/Variables	Treatment	Outcome	Data Quality
Poerio et al., 2018	N=1002; within-subjects design; control stimuli used Heart Rate (HR) Skin Conductance (SC) Questionnaire on presence of tingles and relaxation	3 videos (2 with ASMR, 1 without ASMR)	Greater degree of triggers with sound based and speech based ASMR compared with control Greater reduced HR in triggered vs non-triggered Greater increased SC in triggered vs non-triggered	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Sakurai et al., 2021	N=30; within-subjects design fMRI Questionnaire on presence of frisson vs ASMR, and mood	Classical music and ASMR music	Greater activation of left calcarine cortex, right superior frontal gyrus medial segment, right lingual gyrus, and medial prefrontal cortex (dopamine/oxytocin/relaxation regions) with ASMR music No respondents reported experience of frisson or somatic symptoms with ASM	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Barratt and Davis, 2015	N=475; within-subjects design Qualtrics survey version 36,892 with Lickert style questions on mood, relaxation, stress, and chronic pain; Beck Depression Index (BDI)	ASMR videos (known 53length)	Average 78 out of 100 BDI grade for improved mood 50% improved mood despite no tingles triggered 98% improved relaxation 82% better sleep 70% improved stress 38 out of 475 improved chronic pain 40 out of 475 reported no improvement in chronic pain	Outcomes based on self-report
Engelbregt et al., 2022	N=38; between-subjects design; control group used Shortened Profile of Mood States (POMS); Heart rate (HR); Electrodermal activity (EDA); Electroencephalography (EEG) Mann-Whitney test	2 ASMR videos (length?)	Depression scores decreased No significant difference in Anger, Fatigue, Vigor, & Tension compared with non-triggered group HR reduced for triggered and non-triggered during ASMR stimulus EDA unchanged Increased Beta on EEG for triggered and non-triggered groups	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report

Smejka and Wiggs, 2022	N=1,037; within-subjects design Questionnaires on insomnia, mood, and depression	1 ASMR video (length?)	Increased relaxation Improved mood No difference between the insomnia and depression groups	Outcomes based on self-report
Eid et al., 2022	N=64; between-subjects design State versus Trait Anxiety; Major Depressive Disorder	5-minute ASMR video	Attenuated State Anxiety for ASMR triggered, no difference for non-triggered	Outcomes based on self-report
Hu et al., 2022	N=122; between-subjects design; control group used Addiction Stroop Task; State Anxiety Inventory; Trait Anxiety Inventory;	59 ASMR videos, 1 to 3 minutes long, every 2 to 3 days for 12 weeks	Decreased state anxiety in experiment group Decreased Stroop Task reaction time No significant change in control group	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Seifzadeh et al., 2021	N=10; between-subjects design Heart Rate (HR) Galvanic Skin Conductance (GSC)	1 session of a 20-minute ASMR video	HR decreased in ASMR triggered group GSC reduced in ASMR triggered group	Outcomes based on objective data
Morales et al., 2021	N=176; between-subjects design Spanish Emotion Regulation Questionnaire on suppression, appraisal, reappraisal, and cognitive appraisal	ASMR videos (unknown duration)	Greater increase of cognitive reappraisal in ASMR triggered group than non-triggered group No difference between groups in expressive suppression	Outcomes based on self-report
Rouw and Erfanian, 2017	N=301; within-subjects design Qualtrics survey questions on misophonia reaction	ASMR sound (unknown duration)	Increased positive emotional association with ASMR trigger sounds Unchanged negative emotional association with misophonic trigger sounds	Outcomes based on self-report
Lee et al., 2019	N=15; within-subjects design Electroencephalogram (EEG) to assess sleep state Survey Questionnaire on emotional states	Binaural beat combined with ASMR triggers at 3 different binaural beat-to-ASMR sound level ratios	Greatest increase of Theta power and greatest decrease of Alpha power at 30:60dB ratio compared with 20:60dB & 45:60dB	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report
Paszkiel, et al., 2020	N=9; within-subjects design; control stimuli used Survey Questionnaire on stress level Heart Rate (HR)	4 sessions of 4 different stimuli on 4 different days (silence, rap, relaxing music,	Rap music negatively affects stress level compared with silence (control) Relaxing music and ASMR music calms subjects faster than silence (control)	Outcomes based on objective data and self-report

	Blood Pressure (BP) Electroencephalogram (EEG)	ASMR triggering music)	ASMR music slightly more effective than relaxing music for relaxation Rap music not significantly different than silence in Alpha waves on EEG Both music genres significantly different than silence in Alpha waves on EEG Silence and Relaxing music greater reduction in HR and BP than the other stimuli	
Ditchburn and Bedwell, 2019	N=110; between-group design; control group used Zung's Self Rating Anxiety Scale; CESD-R Scale for depression; Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale ASMR Checklist for test condition trigger selection	1 ASMR video 1 to 2 hours before bed for 7 evenings (10 to 30-minute duration); Mindfulness practice intervention	Significantly higher well-being scores with mindfulness than the control and ASMR Significantly decreased depression scores on all interventions Reduced anxiety in all 3 groups, largest reduction in anxiety scores with mindfulness compared with control group	Outcomes based on self-report

Appendices

Appendix 1

*Post-Trial Questionnaire***ASMR Auditory Training Experiment**

1. Have you ever been formally diagnosed with hearing loss, or do you believe you have some degree of hearing loss?

yes

no

2. Do you use technology for improving hearing difficulties (for example hearing aids, over the counter amplifiers, hearing assistive apps on mobile device, captions, assistive devices loaned to patrons by venues/institutions/museum/theater)?

yes

no

3. Check the boxes for your preferred method of listening skills training:

1 on 1 with an audiologist

1 on 1 with a hearing aid specialist

Life coach

Mental health provider or counselor

Self-paced online course

Self-paced course on printed material

Group learning

Attend a webinar or seminar series

4. Please indicate your responses to the below statements about the ASMR videos.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The videos were easy to access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The number of video sessions was a reasonable time commitment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The sessions were a cost-effective listening skills training regimen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of environmental sounds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of mechanical sounds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of music sounds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to correctly recall groups of words (such as phone number, multi-step directions, repeating what someone said to you).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The videos are beneficial for improving one's comprehension of a conversation.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to understand a message when a part of the message was not heard.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to understand the primary talker when there is competing noise or other voices nearby.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to distinguish sounds in words or words with similar sounds (for example plenty versus twenty).	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to keep up with the pace of a normal conversation and respond appropriately.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Please provide any additional suggestions you have for improving future listening skills training programs like this.					
<input type="text"/>					

Appendix 2

ASMR Auditory Training Program

ASMR Auditory Training Trial
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Thank you for joining this program! Your participation is valuable in gathering information for research. We acknowledge that your participation is voluntary, which helps assure that our data is as unbiased as possible. There is no corporate sponsorship for this research and is approved by the School of Advanced Research Education and Accreditation for the 2023 Masters of Clinical Audiology international cohort. All information gathered is kept confidential, and any personal information will be properly discarded upon completion of the research. Data to be reported will be aggregate in nature, anonymously collected, and not personally identifiable. This trial is physically harmless, but not without some small risks. There is a small chance some videos may sound unpleasant for those with clinically abnormal sound intolerance (for example: hyperacusis or misophonia). Lastly, if the videos are played at very high volume or listened to while you are in a very loud environment, there is a risk of noise induced hearing loss. There are 2 parts to this experiment; the videos are Part One (the Trial), and there will be a brief Post-Trial task (5-minute questionnaire) to complete afterward.

Each session consists of 5 to 6 videos. Please follow the below instructions:

1. Listen & watch each **sound** video for **45 to 60 seconds**.
2. Listen & watch each **conversation/story-telling/role play** video for **7 to 10 minutes**. You do **not** need to finish the entire video if there is more time left at the end of the assigned time. But please do not view more videos than what is listed for the day.
3. Ensure you are connected to the internet with a loudspeaker turned on (if no loudspeaker is embedded in your device, connect an external speaker, or play the audio via your earbuds/headphones/hearing aids if you are more comfortable with this option). Listen to the videos at a comfortable volume (about the same as the volume of normal conversation). Watch the videos while in a quiet space with comfortable ambient lighting.
4. Click the link beside each video description to go directly to the video; a website called YouTube that resembles the image below should appear. You can print this packet and check each box after finishing each video to help you keep track.
5. When you finish all video viewing sessions please complete the survey at: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/VK7R8R3>
6. If you have any issues with links please notify us via email: SAERA2023Cubelo@gmail.com.

Week 1 Day 1

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- 1. Flies buzzing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pc6B8HUEBdQ>
Title: Buzzing Fly Noises by Ram Man
- 2. Garage door: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UAMZJPOKh5k>
Title: Garage Door ASMR by Monkey Trap ASMR
- 3. Helicopter: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H3bwPgSROlw>
Title: 9 Hours Helicopter Sound UH-60 Black Hawk, Black Screen, Dream, ASMR, Meditation, Sleep, Aviation by Jupiter Neon
- 4. Motorbike/ATV: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q1pbySCI95w>
Title: Motorcycle ASMR in Riding Heaven by Schaaf
- 5. Short Story Female Voice (new acquaintance): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MwmYeriOQSE>
Title: ASMR Rude Walmart Cashier grocery store roleplay *fast tapping & soft spoken* by Alexandria ASMR

Week 1 Day 2

- 1. Thunderstorm rainfall: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPZkdNFkNps>
Title: Rain Sound on Window with Thunder Sounds by Relaxing Ambience ASMR
- 2. Truck driving reverse: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kw0XnQPQbL4>
Title: Truck therapy Longest 12-hour truck back up reverse beeping sound white noise by Modern Greaser
- 3. Turn signal: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oiXb8zjtFvs>
Title: ASMR Crown Victoria turn signal sound by Crown Victoria NYC
- 4. Short Story Male Voice (new acquaintance): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=58m2C29rt-k>
Title: ASMR - TAXI DRIVER On A Rainy Night! Role Play by James Matthew ASMR
- 5. Female Sales: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1NquWWRV54w>
Title: ASMR Sales Woman Soft Spoken | Personal Attention by Peace Brain

Week 1 Day 3

- 1. Coins jingling: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UjTzUbPaiQc>
Title: Silver Coins ASMR by Kicking Geese
- 2. Crosswalk Street Light: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5L_CBeevpYw
Title: Audible Crosswalk Sounds! by The Central Texas Railfan
- 3. Car horn: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9pCoQRFFell>
Title: Car Horn - 01 - ASMR – Free Sound Effects (Pack of 3) by Digital Stock Sounds
- 4. Footsteps crunch <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VkZ4eStoaQY>
Title: Experimental ASMR Walking On A Sea Shell Path Outside by TheWaterwhispers
- 5. Short Story Misc Female Voice: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OUYxNT35hWg>
Title: ASMR | What Groceries Do I Buy? by Gibby ASMR

Week 2 Day 1

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- 1. Jackhammer: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vgUHdIA2KCo>
Title: ASMR jackhammer load by Daveo Septic Tank & Plumbing
- 2. Kettle: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TzmenjCnR3k>
Title: Kettle (Tea Pot) Boiling and whistling ASMR - Relaxing Ambience by Ambienette | Ambience & ASMR
- 3. Vacuum: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7JHcHmlvAyI>
Title: Vacuum Cleaner Sound and Video 2022 - 3 Hours - Relax, Sleep, Focus, ASMR by Ambience
- 4. Microwave buttons: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Egg6rT9Vxfo>
Title: (ASMR) Microwave sounds. (with popcorn) by Penhold Productions
- 5. Short Story Misc Male Voice: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EbRo9-gLZLE>
Title: Asmr chill barber gives you a realistic haircut and shave by Deluxeklex ASMR
- 6. Cashier Female: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LhYUqHBhkdE>
Title: ASMR Cashier Roleplay by ASMR COZzyVibeZzz

Week 2 Day 2

- 1. Clock Tic Toc: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oiofG8oVzB8>
Title: Small Alarm Clock Ticking (Half-hour) White Noise (ASMR Alarm Clock Sound) by Repeating Dynamics
- 2. Harp: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cothI9dpGtY>
Title: "Swirling Winds" Original Song | Relaxing Harp Improv with Ambient Wind Sounds | Harp ASMR by Meadow Fox
- 3. Cello: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2cCZoxboF5s>
Title: Music to fall asleep: Cello at 432 Hz, meditation and relaxation 3 hours by Jesse Ahmann Montanna Cellist
- 4. Bass Guitar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bdzMiA1rvgl>
Title: Young the Giant Cough Syrup ASMR Bass & Binaural Guitars by ASMR Intent
- 5. Doctor Appt Female: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=agSm0lkk3cE>
Title: ASMR Checking You in for a Doctors Appointment | Soft Spoken by Jazzy ASMR
- 6. Vowels Male: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=goJQsNgKlhQ>
Title: Speech Therapy ASMR (soft spoken, ear to ear vowel and consonant sounds) by Jim 5 ASMR

Week 2 Day 3

Page 4 of 4

- 1. Xylophone: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8JxSjXB4WNw>
Title: Relaxing Sounds for SLEEP, STUDY, and MEDITATION ASMR Music | TonalASMR | FRISSON by Tonal ASMR
- 2. Clarinet: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vz6w_1esRsQ
Title: [ASMR] Lullaby composed by AI. 1 Hr. Clarinet solo. by 태국 베짚이
- 3. Trumpet: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r79pS6JYXEQ>
Title: Trumpet Jazz ASMR (Surround Music) by 8D Tunes Trumpet Jazz – Topic
- 4. Male & Female Short Story: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7s9Gll4PeLl>
Title: ASMR Cafe Roleplay (Audible conversation W/captions) Real southern restaurant sounds and food! by Rebecca's Beautiful ASMR Addiction
- 5. Male Bartender: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MGGnv0NnEHE>
Title: ASMR Bartender Roleplay with Jazz Music Ambience by ASMR Power of Sound

Appendix 3

Social Media Invitation Post

My name is Christine Cubelo and I'm a student researching a phenomenon known as Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR). The purpose of the research is to fulfill my program's requirement for a Thesis Project, as well as explore ASMR's potential benefit for people with hearing difficulty.

There are 2 Parts to this experiment:

We need volunteers to trial that are:

- Age 18 years or older
- Having perceived hearing difficulty (even if occasionally)
- Diagnosed with any degree of hearing loss
- Fluent in English
- Able to connect to the internet on a device with a loudspeaker

*please share this with someone you know who may like to join

Send an email to SAERA2023Cubelo@gmail.com to enroll or enquire

This research is approved by the School of Advanced Research Education and Accreditation for the 2023 Masters of Clinical Audiology international cohort. All information gathered is kept confidential, and will be properly discarded upon completion of the research. Data collected will be anonymous to the researchers and reported data will not be personally identifiable.

Appendix 4

Clinic Invitation Letter

Greetings,

I am a student of Clinical Audiology and resident of Montgomery County Maryland, seeking the support of local clinics with offering adult patients with perceived hearing difficulties or diagnosed with hearing loss the chance to participate in a unique form of Auditory Training (also known as Auditory Rehabilitation). To date, there is ample research showing the benefits of Auditory Training for helping people with hearing impairment or auditory processing difficulties to build listening skills. For example, there are programs that use Speech Tracking, game-style word recognition apps like Hearing Hunt, and auditory processing activities like LACE (Listening and Communication Enhancement).

As part of completing my Thesis Project, I am exploring the potential benefits of watching online videos that involve varieties of environmental sounds and role-play conversation. These videos fall under a genre known as ASMR, or Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response, and has already been studied to show its therapeutic use in cases of Tinnitus, Misophonia, and even Autism Spectrum Disorder. My present experiment seeks to determine if there are similar therapeutic use of this content for Auditory Training.

The experiment includes:

- Trial: participants are provided a list of weblinks to specific videos to watch 3 days per week for 2 weeks (about 15 to 20 minutes of videos per day). They can choose what 3 days of the week to watch the videos, and what time of day to watch. The Trial runs from January 19, 2023 until May 30, 2023.
- Post-Trial: anonymous responses are collected from participants in an online survey.

This research is approved by the School of Advanced Research Education and Accreditation, Universidad Isabel I, for the 2023 Masters of Clinical Audiology international cohort and being supervised by faculty Dr. Nerea Ortega Castro and Mr. Raul Perez. All information gathered is kept confidential, and will be properly discarded upon completion of the research. Data collected will be anonymous to the researchers and reported data will not be personally identifiable.

The trial is physically harmless, but there is a small chance some videos may sound unpleasant for those with clinically abnormal sound intolerance (for example: hyperacusis). Lastly, if the videos are played at extremely high volume or listened to while in a very loud environment, there is a risk of noise induced hearing loss.

In an effort to limit any additional workload to you and your staff, I could bring printed material to display at your front desk to help bring awareness of this project to your patients. This could include a laminated poster no bigger than 8.5 X 11 inches and/or invitations printed on card stock.

If you have any questions, or to arrange a time for me to visit your clinic, please feel free to contact me directly. I look forward to your response.

Respectfully,

Christine Cubelo, BPS, HIS, COHC
SAERA2023Cubelo@gmail.com

Appendix 5

Post-Trial Response Summary Report Generated by SurveyMonkey

Q1 Have you ever been formally diagnosed with hearing loss, or do you believe you have some degree of hearing loss?

Answered: 14 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
yes	92.86%	13
no	7.14%	1
TOTAL		14

Q2 Do you use technology for improving hearing difficulties (for example hearing aids, over the counter amplifiers, hearing assistive apps on mobile device, captions, assistive devices loaned to patrons by venues/institutions/museum/theater)?

Answered: 14 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
yes	64.29%	9
no	35.71%	5
TOTAL		14

Q3 Check the boxes for your preferred method of listening skills training:

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
1 on 1 with an audiologist	46.15% 6
1 on 1 with a hearing aid specialist	7.69% 1
Life coach	7.69% 1
Mental health provider or counselor	15.38% 2
Self-paced online course	61.54% 8
Self-paced course on printed material	38.46% 5
Group learning	15.38% 2
Attend a webinar or seminar series	30.77% 4
Total Respondents: 13	

Q4 Please indicate your responses to the below statements about the ASMR videos.

	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
The videos were easy to access	71.43% 10	21.43% 3	0.00% 0	7.14% 1	0.00% 0	14	1.43
The number of video sessions was a reasonable time commitment	64.29% 9	35.71% 5	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	14	1.36
The sessions were a cost-effective listening skills training regimen	57.14% 8	21.43% 3	14.29% 2	7.14% 1	0.00% 0	14	1.71
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of environmental sounds	0.00% 0	78.57% 11	14.29% 2	7.14% 1	0.00% 0	14	2.29
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of mechanical sounds	0.00% 0	78.57% 11	21.43% 3	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	14	2.21
The videos were beneficial for improving recognition of music sounds	7.14% 1	71.43% 10	21.43% 3	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	14	2.14
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to correctly recall groups of words (such as phone number, multi-step directions, repeating what someone said to you).	0.00% 0	28.57% 4	28.57% 4	35.71% 5	7.14% 1	14	3.21
The videos are beneficial for improving one's comprehension of a conversation.	7.14% 1	50.00% 7	21.43% 3	14.29% 2	7.14% 1	14	2.64
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to understand a message when a part of the message was not heard.	0.00% 0	50.00% 7	28.57% 4	14.29% 2	7.14% 1	14	2.79
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to understand the primary talker when there is competing noise or other voices nearby.	7.14% 1	64.29% 9	0.00% 0	28.57% 4	0.00% 0	14	2.50
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to distinguish sounds in words or words with similar sounds (for example plenty versus twenty).	0.00% 0	42.86% 6	21.43% 3	28.57% 4	7.14% 1	14	3.00
The videos are beneficial for improving one's ability to keep up with the pace of a normal conversation and respond appropriately.	7.14% 1	42.86% 6	21.43% 3	28.57% 4	0.00% 0	14	2.71

Q5 Please provide any additional suggestions you have for improving future listening skills training programs like this.

Answered: 5 Skipped: 9

1. Difficult to know if videos led to improvement after such a short time. Also on some, I had auto captions on, so may not have been as focused on trying to hear.
2. I don't understand the questions. If you're asking if I had marked improvement in my hearing going forward after watching the videos, the answer is no. But what it did do was to really relax me so that I was sleeping better despite recent hearing loss anxiety, snoring husband and menopause! It gave me more of an appreciation for sounds, and that I can still hear them (and yes, I think I am noticing the birds singing more). And it made me appreciate my good ear. But I will keep doing them to see if they impact my conversational and background noise situations.
3. I had no trouble hearing any of the videos. The "tapping" on things could get irritating if you had to listen long.
4. I've known the principles of ASMR for years, and use some ASMR apps to help me sleep. And they key characteristic of people talking in an ASMR video (all of the "person talking" videos were ASMR) is NOT to be able to understand what the speaker is saying, but rather to hear relaxing, soft vocal tone, crackling paper, repetitive sounds, etc. etc.....but the goal is definitely not comprehension: Comprehension actually defeats the purpose of ASMR! Consequently, when I see ASMR, I make no attempt to understand the speaker. So I didn't go into the exercise making any attempt to understand the speakers (and even if I did attempt such I would have understood very little—ASMR speakers' priority is tone/gentleness, etc. : not being understood. And I really wasn't sure what the objective of the exercise was, so I was unsure as to "what I should be looking for" when listening to the sounds, music, or voices. I may have been highly biased due to the fact that I've focused on the virtues of ASMR for so long. But even with this bias, from my standpoint, I really don't feel that this exercise generated any suggestions for improving future listening skills training programs. Sorry!
5. More music for people with cochlear implants. Without the videos I would not have recognized some of the sounds in part because electric sounds do not render real life sounds very well. The USA accents were not the same as I experience in Australia, so different accents would be appropriate. Some of the sounds such as street crossing at lights are not the same in Australia.